

Fast Fourier Transform on the Versat CGRA

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Abstract—In this paper we present a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithm for the Versat architecture, a small and low power Coarse Grained Reconfigurable Array (CGRA). This approach targets ultra low energy applications such as those found in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), where using a GPU or FPGA accelerator is out of the question. The implementation chosen was the Radix-2 FFT, and uses 32-bit integer precision in the Q1.31 format. The Versat program creates two base hardware datapaths for the two basic steps of the algorithm: the complex multiplication and the complex addition steps. These datapaths are partially reconfigured during execution. The program has been written in assembly and has 873 instructions. It is fully parameterizable with the number of datapoints, FFT window size, overlap size and memory pointers for reading and writing back the data to the external memory. The results show that the new Versat core is 9.4x smaller than an ARM Cortex A9 core, runs the algorithm on average 18x faster and consumes 219.51x less energy.

Keywords—FFT, reconfigurable computing, coarse-grained reconfigurable arrays

I. INTRODUCTION

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is an algorithm for efficiently computing the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of a digitized signal, and very useful to perform spectral analysis. It is used in many signal processing applications such as filters, audio and video pre and post processing as well as encoders and decoders. The DFT converts the data from its original domain (often time or space) into a representation in the frequency domain. The FFT algorithm became popular in 1965, although its principles had been developed back in 1805 [1]. After Gilbert Strang said that it is "the most important numerical algorithm of our lifetime" [2], in 1994 it was added to Top 10 Algorithms of the 20th Century by the IEEE Computing in Science & Engineering journal [3]. One of the most widely used FFT algorithms is the Cooley-Tukey algorithm, addressed in this paper.

Three relevant examples of low energy FFT applications are (1) wireless communications [4], (2) sensor biosignal data processing [5] and (3) Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) [6], [7]. Since there is an increasing scientific interest in Big Data (i.e., very large datasets), real-time data processing emphasize the needed for fast FFT computation. This problem can be attenuated by the use of hardware accelerators.

The FFT algorithm has been accelerated using Graphics Processor Units (GPUs) [8], [9], [10] and using Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) [11], [12], [13]. Although these implementations have been shown to improve performance and energy consumption over General Purpose

Processors (GPPs) implementations, they can hardly be used in ultra low energy scenarios, such as WSNs. Local processing of sensor data allows reducing the data that needs to be transmitted. Thus, it is more efficient, in terms of time and energy, to run the FFT algorithm in a distributed fashion rather than in a centralized way. Since WSN nodes are extremely constrained in terms of compute power and energy consumption, a smaller and more power efficient accelerator should be used, such as a Coarse Grained Reconfigurable Array (CGRA). A dedicated hardware accelerator may also be used but its lack of programmability can become a serious liability in the long run.

This paper presents an in-depth study of a fully parameterizable implementation of the FFT algorithm for a previously published CGRA – the Versat architecture [14]. The Versat CGRA features a relatively low number of functional units, achieving a very small area footprint and low energy consumption. Reconfiguration is quasi-static (occurring only after complete loop nests are run) and partial (only the configuration words that differ from the previous configuration are changed). Unlike other CGRAs, which are programmed by pre-compiling configurations for their programmable hardware, Versat uses a very small 16-instruction controller, which generates and/or modifies hardware configurations at runtime. The Versat controller can be programmed in assembly language or using a small C++ subset for which a compiler has been described in [15]. The FFT software for Versat has been written in assembly.

The proposed algorithm computes the FFT on a sliding window over a long discrete signal. It makes use of Data-Level Parallelism (DLP) and Instruction-Level Parallelism (ILP). As is demonstrated in this paper, the algorithm is highly scalable with the window size and signal length, with increasing acceleration compared to GPP implementations. The data format is 32-bit fixed-point in a Q1.31 organization. The Versat architecture does not support floating point data, yet.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the FFT algorithm. Section III briefly outlines the Versat architecture. Section IV presents the proposed algorithm. Section V presents implementation and performance results. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. FFT THEORY

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is an expedite way to compute the Discrete Fourier Transform of a discrete time signal. There are many implementations of the FFT algorithm. For this work the Radix-2 FFT algorithm has been chosen, due

to its simplicity. In the next section, a formal description of the DFT is presented, and in the section after, the Cooley-Tukey Radix-2 FFT algorithm is described.

A. Discrete Fourier Transform

The Discrete Fourier Transform $X(k)$ of a discrete signal $x(n)$ having N samples is given by

$$X(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} W_N^{kn} x(n), \quad 0 \leq k \leq N-1, \quad (1)$$

where the coefficients W_N^k are given by

$$W_N^k = e^{-j \frac{2\pi k}{N}}. \quad (2)$$

The most obvious way to compute a DFT point $X(k)$ is to perform N complex multiplications ($4N$ real multiplications) and $N-1$ complex additions ($2N-2$ real additions). Because one needs to compute N points of the DFT, the algorithm complexity is $O(N^2)$. Attending to the coefficients symmetry (equation 3) and periodicity (equation 4), it is possible achieve a better algorithm, and the Cooley-Tukey FFT Algorithm, explained in the next section, is just that.

$$W_N^{k+\frac{N}{2}} = -W_N^k \quad (3)$$

$$W_N^{k+N} = W_N^k \quad (4)$$

B. Cooley-Tukey FFT Algorithm

The DFT computation of N points can be decomposed in two independent DFT computations of $N/2$ points, for N even, separating the points which have even indices from the ones that have odd indices. Equation (1) can thus be re-written as

$$X(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{(N/2)-1} W_N^{k(2n)} x(2n) + \sum_{n=0}^{(N/2)-1} W_N^{k(2n+1)} x(2n+1). \quad (5)$$

From equation (2) it can be derived that $W_N^{2k} = W_{N/2}^k$, and equation (5) can be re-written as

$$X(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{(N/2)-1} W_{N/2}^{kn} f_e(n) + W_N^k \sum_{n=0}^{(N/2)-1} W_{N/2}^{kn} f_o(n), \quad (6)$$

where $f_e(n) = x(2n)$ and $f_o(n) = x(2n+1)$. Hence, equation (6) can be written as

$$X(k) = F_e(k) + W_N^k F_o(k), \quad 0 \leq k \leq N-1. \quad (7)$$

Since $F_e(k)$ and $F_o(k)$ are periodic with period $N/2$, and taking into account the coefficients' symmetry, according to equations (3) and (4), the previous expression can be re-written as

$$X(k) = F_e(k) + W_N^k F_o(k), \\ X\left(k + \frac{N}{2}\right) = F_e(k) - W_N^k F_o(k), \quad 0 \leq k \leq \frac{N}{2} - 1. \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) proves that it is possible to decompose an N -point DFT into a weighted sum of two $N/2$ -point DFTs. This procedure can be applied recursively until the simplest case of a 2-point DFT is reached. This happens after $\log_2(N)$ recursion levels, which explains why this FFT algorithm is called *Radix-2*. In this algorithm there are $(N/2)\log_2(N)$ complex multiplications and $N\log_2(N)$ complex additions. Therefore, the Cooley-Tukey algorithm has complexity $O(N\log(N))$.

A 2-point FFT computed in this way is shown in figure 1. This is called a butterfly diagram because of its shape. The input data is on the left, while the output data is on the right. All data are complex numbers. The edges represent values which may be weighted by the coefficients W_N and -1 . Where edges merge, their corresponding values are added. For optimization, an edge having the coefficient -1 is simply subtracted from the other merging edge.

Fig. 1. Butterfly diagram.

A graphical example of the Cooley-Tukey algorithm applied to an 8-point signal x is shown in figure 2. The recursion levels map to stages. In this example, there are $\log_2(8) = 3$ stages. Each stage have distinctive groups of butterflies called blocks. The first stage has 4 blocks of a single butterfly, the second stage has 2 blocks of 2 butterflies and the third stage has a single block of 4 butterflies.

Fig. 2. Cooley-Tukey algorithm applied to an 8-point signal x

The Versat FFT kernel implements the Cooley-Tukey algorithm by splitting a basic butterfly structure in two steps:

- 1) Complex multiplication step: the datapoints stored at odd addresses are multiplied by the coefficients
- 2) Complex addition step: the datapoints stored at even addresses are added and subtracted from the results of the first step to yield 2 result datapoints

III. VERSAT ARCHITECTURE

The Versat architecture is presented in detail in [14]. Here, only a brief description is presented for self containability reasons. The top level entity is shown in figure 3. Referring to this figure, the Controller executes the program stored in the 2048x32bit Program Memory (PM). The communication between a host system and Versat is done through the Control Register File (CRF), consisting of 16 registers, R0 through R15. The host uses the CRF to pass parameters to Versat programs, initiate their execution and check if they have finished. The Data Engine (DE) is where most computations take place. The controller writes new DE configurations to the Configuration Module (CM). These configurations can be selected for execution and/or partially modified. The Direct Memory Access (DMA) module is used to access the external memory and transfer data/instructions/configurations to/from the DE/PM/CM, respectively. The DE receives commands from the controller and informs the controller of its status. The DE is run many times during the execution of a program, for many different DE configurations.

Fig. 3. Versat top-level entity.

A. Controller

The Versat controller runs the kernel algorithms and is responsible for the overall control of the system, especially the reconfiguration process. It performs loads and stores (from/to the Control Bus), a few arithmetic and logic operations, and branch instructions. The controller has not been designed for high performance. Its instruction set consists of just 16 instructions and its performance is just enough for controlling the main steps of the algorithms, reconfiguring the DE and operating the DMA; data intensive computations are done in the DE.

B. Data Engine

The Data Engine (DE) is a 32-bit architecture and comprises 15 functional units (FUs) as shown in figure 4. There are four 2048x32bit dual port embedded memories, six ALUs, four multipliers and one barrel shifter. The outputs of all FUs are concatenated to form a 19x32-bit Data Bus. (Since each

memory contributes two outputs, there are $2*4+6+4+1=19$ bus sections.) Each FU input can be configured to select any of the 19 sections of the bus – this implements a full mesh topology and avoids contention on the Data Bus.

Fig. 4. Versat data engine.

The embedded memories have one Address Generator Unit (AGU) for each port. The AGU can support two-level for loop nests. It is possible to configure and run each AGU independently. The AGU parameters are described in table I.

TABLE I. ADDRESS GENERATOR UNIT PARAMETERS.

Parameter	Size (bits)	Description
Start	11	Memory start address. Default value is 0.
Per	5	Number of iterations of the inner loop, aka Period. Default is 1 (no inner loop).
Duty	5	Number of cycles in a period (Per) that the memory is enabled. Default is 1.
Incr	11	Increment for the inner loop. Default is 0.
Iter	11	Number of iterations of the outer loop. Default is 1.
Shift	11	Additional increment in the end of each period. Note that Per+Shift is the increment of the outer loop. Default is 0.
Delay	5	Number of clock cycles that the AGU must wait before starting to work. Used to compensate different latencies in the converging branches of the configured hardware datapaths. Default is 0.
Reverse	1	Bit-wise reversion of the generated address. Certain applications like the FFT work with mirrored addresses. Default is 0.

By configuration, the AGU can be bypassed and the memory port address is input by the other port. What this actually does is to provide Versat with the capability of working with pointers, as these can be computed in the DE and routed to any embedded memory to be used as addresses. In addition, the number sequences generated by an AGU can be output to the DE for general purposes, instead of being used as addresses. This exploits the ability of the AGUs to generate synchronization sequences, making it possible to use them to synchronize FUs in the DE. The two ports can be independently configured to read and/or write the memories. The write configuration includes the selection of a data bus section to be written in the memory.

There are two types of ALUs, which differ in the supported operations. Two ALUs are of type I, supporting basic arithmetic and logic operations, while four ALUs are of type II, supporting basic operations plus the same operations where one operand is internally connected to the ALU output itself, freeing the respective input to be used for conditional control. This implements internal feedback and conditional execution to type II ALUs. For example, the basic operation of *addition* can be turned into a conditional accumulate operation: the ALU can register or accumulate the value present at one of its inputs, depending on the value present at the other input. In another example, the *minimum* operation can be used to detect and register the minimum value of a sequence present at one

of the ALU inputs, while the control input qualifies the value present at the data input. For example, if an AGU is used to generate a control sequence for the conditional ALU input, the computation of the minimum and registration of the result at the ALU output will happen only in certain time instants; at other instants the last computed minimum is kept.

The multipliers take two 32-bit operands and produce a 64-bit result, of which only 32 bits are used. It is possible to choose the upper or lower 32-bit part of the result. It is also possible multiply the output by two, which is useful to keep a Q1.31 fixed-point format used in many DSP algorithms.

For the barrel shifter, one operand is the word to be shifted and the other operand is the shift size. The barrel shifter is configured with the shift direction (left or right) and the right shift type (arithmetic or logic).

Each FU has a latency due to pipelining: 2 cycles for the ALU, 3 cycles for the multiplier and 1 cycle for the barrel shifter. Thus, when configuring a datapath in the DE, it is necessary to take into account the latency of each datapath branch, and compensate for any mismatches when branches with different latencies converge. To do this, the AGUs have the *Delay* parameter explained in table I. The branch latency is the sum of its FU latencies.

To control the DE, its control and status registers are used. It is possible to initialize/run the FUs by setting bits 0/1 of the control register, respectively. Bits 2-20 select the FUs to initialize or run. Since there are 11 operation FUs and 4 memory FUs and each of the 2 memory ports can be controlled independently, there are $11+2 \times 4=19$ bits in the DE control register for selecting the FUs. To check the DE, its status register is used. The status register indicates which AGUs have ended execution (bits 0 to 7).

C. Configuration Module

The configurations of the DE are stored in the Configuration Module (CM). The CM comprises the configuration register file, the configuration shadow register and the configuration memory. The configuration register file is used by the Versat controller to write configuration words to the DE (partial reconfiguration). The shadow register allows keeping the currently active DE configuration while a future configuration is being created in the configuration register. The configuration memory can be used to save 64 frequently used DE configurations. A configuration in the configuration register file can be saved in the configuration memory in 1 clock cycle and reloaded later for reuse also in 1 clock cycle.

D. DMA

The Versat controller uses the DMA module to access an external memory and transfer programs, data and configurations. Though Versat can load configurations from the external memory, this feature has never been used as Versat is designed to generate its own configurations and does not in principle need to access configurations from the external memory. The maximum block transfer size is 256 words of 32 bits. The DMA can work in parallel with the controller and the DE.

IV. THE FFT KERNEL

The FFT kernel follows the algorithm given in section II, creating and partially reconfiguring two basic hardware datapaths that realize the *complex multiplication* and *complex addition* steps of the algorithm. In fact, two versions of each datapath have been created to enable ping-pong data processing. Another datapath is used to initially reorder the datapoints by reverting the bits of their addresses. The kernel is written in the Versat assembly language and it is 873 instructions long.

The datapath to initially reorder the data is shown in figure 5). The address generators of the source memories MEM2 and MEM3 read the datapoints with the Reverse parameter set to 1 (table I), and the address generators of the destination memories MEM0 and MEM1 write them sequentially. Concurrently, the table of coefficients is copied from MEM2 to MEM0, so that either can be accessed during ping-pong processing.

Fig. 5. Datapath for read the initial datapoints with mirrored addresses.

The Versat controller plays an important role in complex kernels like the present FFT kernel. It is responsible for generating the datapaths, reconfiguring them and controlling the algorithm. Namely, it controls the outer loops over all stages and, in some cases, over all blocks in a stage.

First, the four datapaths are created and stored in the configuration memory. They are very similar two by two, swapping only the memories that are used for reading with the ones that are used for storing the data. This is done while data is being DMA transferred into the DE.

After reading a number of parameters from the CRF (number of datapoints, window and overlap sizes and addresses to read/write data in the external memory), as passed by the host, the program instructs the DMA to load the first datapoint chunk values in memories MEM2 and MEM3. Real parts go for MEM2 and imaginary parts for MEM3, not exceeding the 1024 lower addresses. Coefficient values are also DMA transferred into memory MEM2, occupying at most the 1024 higher addresses. Then the data is reordered and placed in memories MEM0 and MEM1 while the coefficients are copied to MEM0, using the reordering datapath explained before.

The datapath in figure 6 implements the complex multiplication step, reading the data from MEM0 (real part) and MEM1 (imaginary part) and coefficients from MEM2 (real and imaginary parts), and writing the result back in MEM0 and MEM1. Its configuration is loaded from the configuration memory into the configuration register in one clock cycle, partially reconfigured, and shifted to the shadow configuration register in another cycle. The datapath forms a read-multiply-add-write pipeline with four multiplications and two additions in parallel in the respective stages, combining DLP and ILP.

Fig. 6. Datapath for the complex multiplication step.

Next, the datapath that performs the complex addition step, shown in figure 7, is loaded. This datapath performs the two complex additions in the butterfly diagram of figure 1. Note that MEM0 (real part) and MEM1 (imaginary part) have the original data in the even addresses and the original data multiplied by the coefficients in the odd addresses. Therefore the data in the even addresses is added and subtracted to the data in the odd addresses to produce the two butterfly outputs. The results are placed in MEM2 (real part) and MEM3 (imaginary part). The parallel additions exploit DLP while the read-compute-write pipeline exploits ILP.

Fig. 7. Datapath for the complex addition step.

After both steps are run, the controller increments the outer loop and the two steps are applied again, now from MEM2 and MEM3 to MEM0 and MEM1. This process is repeated until all stages are processed. Every time the kernel needs more data, the current results are stored in the external memory and new datapoints are loaded into the DE memories.

Because AGU parameter Period has only 5 bits (table I), there is need to break the two step computations in several parts for some stages. This is because the two nested loops that can be executed in the DE are used to go over all blocks and all datapoints within a block. If there are more than $2^5 = 32$ points within a block then the inner loop cannot be used. Only the iterations loop is used and the DE needs to be reconfigured for each block. In order to save reconfiguration time, the controller uses partial reconfiguration. Additionally, if an FFT window cannot fit into the DE memories, the FFT computation is divided into several smaller FFTs and several other steps to merge the results.

After all stages are processed, the controller instructs the DMA to transfer the results to the external memory, using the respective address in the CRF passed by the host. Then, a new datapoint chunk is loaded and the whole process starts again, until all datapoints are processed and stored in the

external memory. When this happens, the algorithm terminates. Before returning to the boot ROM memory, the controller clears register R0 in the CRF, which signals the host that Versat has finished execution.

V. RESULTS

In this section, design and performance results are presented. Versat has been designed as an IP core, which can be integrated in a System on Chip (SoC). Results on core area, frequency and power are given. Versat's performance for the present FFT algorithm is measured and compared to a widely used embedded processor: the ARM Cortex A9 processor.

A. IP core Implementation Results

Versat has been designed using a UMC 130nm process and its main features are shown in table II: technology node (N), silicon area (A), embedded memory (RAM), frequency of operation (F) and power (P). For the sake of comparison we also show the features of a previous Versat version and of the ARM Cortex A9 processor, implemented in a 40nm technology and optimized for power [16].

The Versat frequency and power results for the 130nm process have been obtained using the Cadence IC design and simulation tools. The frequency is reported by the place and route tool, which produces a netlist with back-annotated layout information. Power is obtained by simulating this netlist to get node activities, and then computing a power figure. For synthesis, the Encounter RTL Compiler tool (v11.20) has been used. For place and route, the Encounter Design Implementation tool (v11.10) has been used. For simulation, the NCSIM simulator (v12.10) has been used. To better compare with the ARM processor, the last row in table II shows the Versat features scaled to a 40nm technology. These results have been obtained by applying scaling rules as explained in [17].

TABLE II. INTEGRATED CIRCUIT IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

Core	N(nm)	A(mm ²)	RAM(kB)	F(MHz)	P(mW)
Versat [14]	130	4.2	46.34	170	99
Versat [here]	130	5.2	46.34	170	132
ARM Cortex A9 [16]	40	4.6	65.54	800	500
Versat [here, scaled]	40	0.49	46.34	553	41

From the above results, we conclude that the current Versat core is 9.4x smaller than the ARM core and consumes 12.2x less power, assuming both cores are clocked at their work frequencies. The Versat power has been obtained by simulating the present FFT algorithm. The results show that the current Versat version is 24% larger than the previous version presented in [14], and consumes 32% more power. The ARM power figure is an average value reported in [16].

B. Performance Results

To study our solution's performance we successively computed the FFT on a sliding window of a certain size over a large sequence of datapoints randomly generated. Two consecutive windows may overlap for a number of datapoints, called the overlap size. The experiments consider varying the number of data points, window and overlap size. We measured the execution time for both the Versat and the ARM Cortex A9 systems, which is given by the number of clock cycles divided

by the clock frequency in the 40nm process SoC, according to table II.

The Xilinx Zynq 7010 platform has been used to measure the performance of both the Versat core and the ARM Cortex A9 core, available in the Zynq platform as a hard macro. The ARM results have been obtained using a system timer in a bare metal implementation of the FFT algorithm. The Versat core has been added as a peripheral of the ARM core, controlled from its AXI slave interface and accessing the external memory via its AXI master interface. The ARM core has been used to measure the Versat execution time using the same system timer.

In figure 8, we show the execution time as a function of the number of datapoints in a static window, i.e., no sliding occurs. These results show that, for both the Versat and ARM cores, the execution time scales according to the algorithm's complexity ($N \log_2(N)$).

Fig. 8. Execution time vs. FFT static window size.

The execution time of both cores is affected by the size of their internal memories. In the Versat case it is the size of its embedded memories and in the ARM case it is its cache system, L1 plus L2. This phenomenon is visible in figure 9, where the speedup versus the number of datapoints is shown. The speedup SU is computed by

$$SU = \frac{N_A f_v}{N_v f_A},$$

where N_A and N_V are the number of execution clock cycles for the ARM and Versat cores, respectively, and f_A and f_V are the operation frequencies for the ARM and Versat cores, respectively. After the FFT window size reaches the capacity of the Versat memories, the speedup declines and starts increasing again when it reaches the ARM's L1 cache size. For 16k points the speedup is more than 17. This shows that Versat can manage concurrent data transfers from external memory better than the ARM core.

In figure 10, we show the execution time as a function of the overlap size for a 1024-point sliding window. For this experiment, the execution time grows much faster for the ARM core compared to the Versat core.

Fig. 9. Speedup vs. FFT static window size.

Fig. 10. Execution time vs. overlap size for a 1024-point sliding window.

The speedup is higher than in the previous experiment and is linear in the overlap size, according to figure 11. This is because Versat always keeps the overlapped points in its memories for the next FFT window, transferring only the remaining points. Instead, the ARM system uses its cache and data prefetch mechanisms for managing data streaming automatically, which proves to be a worse solution.

In figure 12, we show the execution time as a function of the sliding window size. Initially the execution time raises rapidly as the size of the internal memories is reached. After that the increase rate slows down.

The speedup as a function of the sliding window size is illustrated by figure 13. As the sliding window reaches the capacity of the Versat memories, the speedup drops, while the ARM caches and prefetch mechanisms continue to work well. However, as the window size increases, the ARM core reaches its own internal memory limitations for streaming data, and the speedup increases steadily after that.

The energy ratio ER of using Versat compared to using

Fig. 11. Speedup vs. overlap size for a 1024-point sliding window.

Fig. 12. Execution time vs. sliding window size for half window overlap.

Fig. 13. Execution time vs. sliding window size for half window overlap.

the ARM Cortex A9 processor, that is, the ratio of the energy consumed by the ARM core and the energy consumed by the Versat core to execute the FFT algorithm, can be computed by

$$ER = SU \frac{P_A}{P_V} = 219.51,$$

where $SU = 18$ is the average speedup, and P_A and P_V are the power consumption of the ARM and Versat cores, respectively, as given in table II for the 40nm process.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an in-depth study of an FFT algorithm targeting the Versat CGRA has been presented. Although there are quite a few solutions for accelerating this algorithm in GPUs and FPGAs, these are not good solutions for high performance / ultra low energy embedded applications. For example, the FFT algorithm is useful in wireless sensor network nodes, which are severely constrained in terms of compute capabilities and energy consumption.

The Versat architecture has limited compute resources but it is extremely flexible to program. In fact, Versat can be programmed like a traditional controller, where the program itself creates and partially reconfigures hardware datapaths in its data engine. The full mesh topology of the data engine is easy to deal with by programmers. Versat is capable of useful acceleration at low clock rates and, given its small size, it can save orders of magnitude in energy. It is designed to be a programmable alternative to dedicated hardware accelerators, eliminating the risk of design errors. This paper briefly outlines the Versat architecture.

The proposed FFT algorithm comprises two main steps: the complex multiplication and the complex addition steps. The algorithm uses a basic hardware datapath for each of these steps. The complex multiplication datapath multiplies the datapoints with odd addresses by the FFT coefficients. The complex addition datapath adds the complex multiplication result and the odd address datapoints, and subtracts the complex multiplication result from even address datapoints. These results are stored in the Versat embedded memories to be used in the next FFT stage. In order to improve performance, the basic datapaths are runtime reconfigured to swap origin and destination memories in a ping-pong fashion, and to change the addresses for accessing data from the memories.

Our results show that Versat is 9.4x smaller than an ARM Cortex A9 processor, and runs the FFT algorithm on average 18x faster, while consuming 219.51x less energy. It should be clear from these numbers that GPUs and FPGAs cannot compete in this arena, and that the presented solution is useful in applications where cost and energy consumption are crucial.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Michael Heideman, Don Johnson, and C Burrus. Gauss and the history of the fast fourier transform. *IEEE ASSP Magazine*, 1(4):14–21, 1984.
- [2] Gilbert Strang. Wavelets. *American Scientist*, 82(3):250–255, 1994.
- [3] Jack Dongarra and Francis Sullivan. Guest editors introduction: The top 10 algorithms. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 2(1):22–23, 2000.
- [4] Fabio Garzia, Waqar Hussain, and Jari Nurmi. Crema: A coarse-grain reconfigurable array with mapping adaptiveness. In *Field Programmable Logic and Applications, 2009. FPL 2009. International Conference on*, pages 708–712. IEEE, 2009.
- [5] Kunjan Patel, Séamas McGettrick, and Chris J Bleakley. Syscore: A coarse grained reconfigurable array architecture for low energy biosignal processing. In *Field-Programmable Custom Computing Machines (FCCM), 2011 IEEE 19th Annual International Symposium on*, pages 109–112. IEEE, 2011.
- [6] Turkmen Canli, Ajay Gupta, and Ashfaq Khokhar. Power efficient algorithms for computing fast fourier transform over wireless sensor networks. In *Computer Systems and Applications, 2006. IEEE International Conference on.*, pages 549–556. IEEE, 2006.
- [7] Xi Xu, Rashid Ansari, and Ashfaq Khokhar. Power-efficient algorithms for fourier analysis over random wireless sensor network. In *Distributed Computing in Sensor Systems (DCOSS), 2012 IEEE 8th International Conference on*, pages 109–115. IEEE, 2012.
- [8] Kenneth Moreland and Edward Angel. The FFT on a GPU. In *Proceedings of the ACM SIGGRAPH/EUROGRAPHICS conference on Graphics hardware*, pages 112–119. Eurographics Association, 2003.
- [9] M Doggett, W Heidrich, W Mark, and A Schilling. The FFT on a GPU.
- [10] Ondrej Fialka and Martin Cadik. FFT and convolution performance in image filtering on GPU. In *Information Visualization, 2006. IV 2006. Tenth International Conference on*, pages 609–614. IEEE, 2006.
- [11] Chu Chao, Zhang Qin, Xie Yingke, and Han Chengde. Design of a high performance FFT processor based on FPGA. In *Proceedings of the 2005 Asia and South Pacific Design Automation Conference*, pages 920–923. ACM, 2005.
- [12] Zhijian Sun, Xuemei Liu, and Zhongxing Ji. The design of radix-4 FFT by FPGA. In *Intelligent Information Technology Application Workshops, 2008. IITAW'08. International Symposium on*, pages 765–768. IEEE, 2008.
- [13] Zahra Haddad Derafshi, Javad Frounchi, and Hamed Taghipour. A high speed FPGA implementation of a 1024-point complex FFT processor. In *Computer and Network Technology (ICCNT), 2010 Second International Conference on*, pages 312–315. IEEE, 2010.
- [14] J.D. Lopes and J.T. de Sousa. Versat, a minimal coarse-grain reconfigurable array. In *Proc. of the 12th Int. Meeting on High Performance Computing for Computational Science, VECPAR, Porto, Portugal, June 2016*.
- [15] Rui Santiago, José T. de Sousa, and João D. Lopes. Compiler for the versat architecture. In *XIII Jornadas de Sistemas Reconfiguráveis*, pages 41–48, January 2017.
- [16] Wei Wang and Tanima Dey. A survey on ARM Cortex A processors. https://www.cs.virginia.edu/skadron/cs8535_s11/ARM_Cortex.pdf. Accessed 2016-04-16.
- [17] S. Borkar. Design challenges of technology scaling. *IEEE Micro*, 19(4):23–29, Jul 1999.